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Internationalisation of German VET providers: New Business Models for New Markets?

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Abstract

Context: A special interest of the funding program “Internationalization of VET” by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research is to support the development of context-related and need-driven business models. This is a special challenge for the involved German VET providers (small and medium sized enterprises) which usually are either internationally consolidated and open up to new markets or nationally experienced. German educational providers in international contexts seem to lack consolidation according to a long-term expansion of their portfolio and also they lack drivers for innovation and for change management within the organisations (Interview with DLR PT, 17.04.2018). The central question is: How do German VET providers develop, adapt and modify their service offer abroad and which role play “promoters” in this process?

Approach: Based on the „business model generation approach” by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur we present and analyse an example of a developed business model. The theoretical approach can be located in service science, a heterogeneous research concept. Besides, the promoters of innovation and their allocation are analysed.

Results: Starting with a clear idea of a new business model, the analysed project uses several further adaptations of the service to find a customer and context oriented product. Different stakeholders are involved in the process of development and promoters are able to engage in the procedure.

Conclusion: In the context of VET-related services, the business model of the analysis case works so far although the provided service is not part of the standard offers of the company. The service is being adopted to the target market which strengthens the thesis that this procedure is vital for the success of transfer.

Keywords

business model development; service science; program evaluation and research; VET-related services; internationalization of VET

1 Introduction and research approach

The starting point of this article is the current discussion on transfer of vocational education and training. Debates on youth unemployment and skill shortage encourage political discussions and scientific discourses about the German model of dual vocational training and how it could be applied in other education systems (Gessler et al. 2019; Peters 2019). Dual training models are being regarded as a chance to control challenges like youth unemployment and problems in school-to-work transition. At the latest since the financial crisis of 2007/2008 when youth unemployment increased drastically, the issue of employability and innovative ways of qualification became relevant.

In transfer research, it is discussed whether VET can be transferred to the context of other countries. The policy transfer literature refers to findings from politics (e.g., Barabasch/Wolf 2012); different concepts containing strategies and elements have been developed focusing main components of the German VET system regarding transfer (Euler 2013; Pilz 2017); but only few studies are available which analyse transfer processes in detail (see also Gessler 2017).

From the German perspective, there is the problem of German companies abroad to find skilled workers and specialists. The companies need qualified professionals locally where the production takes place. For example, the German Chamber of Commerce in China notes that one of the hardest challenge for German companies in China is to find skilled workers: *“Three out of four companies regard [...] finding qualified staff as a major problem“* (German Chamber of Commerce China, 2016).

The funding program “internationalization of VET”, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), wants to dedicate this challenge. The program comprises three different funding priorities:

- a) Projects: In cooperation with institutions from the target countries (which do not have bilateral cooperation with the BMBF so far), a)-projects probe in how far bilateral agreement between BMBF and other countries’ governments (“Berufsbildungskooperationen”) could be expedient. The need is notified by requests from the countries’ official bodies themselves.
- b) Projects focus these countries which do have a bilateral vocational training cooperation with the BMBF already.¹ Pilot actions and model-like realizations of reform plans regarding the countries’ VET systems are supposed to be supported in a concrete, systematic and demand-driven manner. Developments of curricula, training courses etc. can be the target in b)-projects.
- c) Projects are funded for implementing education and training services (initial vocational education and training as well as further education). It is a main objective to support the development of context-related and need-driven business models, which is a special challenge for the involved VET providers as they mostly lack the experience of offering services abroad.

¹ The European ones are Greece, Italy, Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia and non-European are India, China, Costa Rica, Georgia, Russia, South Africa, Thailand and Mexico.

The research questions of our concomitant research ask which contexts and cooperations enable the projects to successfully² reach their goals, which challenges they face and which strategies of problem-solving are expedient.

The idea of the c)-projects is to establish VET-related services abroad to fulfil different demands: qualification and, in sight of the big picture, to make it possible to diffuse the approaches or concepts in the countries' education system. In this analysis, our research questions is: *How do German VET providers develop, adapt and modify their service offer abroad and which role play „promoters" is this process?* This paper presents and analyzes the business models that are part of the c)-project strategies, based on the „business model generation approach" by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur (2010).

2 Theoretical approach

2.1 Business model

Our theoretical research concept is located in a business model approach which is called "Business Model Canvas" due to its way of presentation (Osterwalder/Pigneur 2010), which links to Service Science. The economical and societal meaning of services is undeniable – the role of the tertiary sector in relation to the secondary sector grew constantly during the last decades.³ However, the question arises whether the sectoral economic shifts have already been adequately perceived and processed in science, especially with regard to vocational educational services.

Lusch und Vargo 2006 (p. 4) define service as "the application of specialized competences (knowledge and skills), through deeds, processes, and performances for the benefit of another entity or the entity itself". Service itself offers a range from person-related services to complex business related services. A general accepted definition of service is not easy to be found. Furthermore, a demarcation of Service Science is challenging: Apart from Service Engineering, SDL (Service Dominant Logic), Social Science Services and SSME (service science, management, and engineering), there are far more approaches for exploring services. In our research, the concept of Service Engineering is applied: Service Engineering combines management and engineering approaches to develop (industrial and non-industrial) services to open up new markets. The weakness of Service Science is that it is a general and no domain-specific approach. This means that we need to create a VET-theory related Service Science for our research using the theoretical concepts described below.

For the conceptual work, some of the c)-projects work with the Business Model Canvas (BMC) already. Osterwalder and Pigneurs (2010) approach of the BMC is to compile an image of the own business model to improve the understanding of processes, relations and problems by visualizing. The scheme of the BMC is visualized in figure 1. The Canvas is all about thinking in categories of business and answer the following questions:

- Value Propositions: What's compelling about the proposition? Why do customers buy and use it?

² The success of a project needs an operational definition for this paper which is: Projects are able to implement their service (product) on the target market.

³ In Germany, the share of the tertiary sector in the total employment increased from 1970 up to the present from 45.1 percent to 74.1 percent (Fonger et al. 2017, 7).

- Channels: How are the propositions promoted, sold and delivered?
- Customer Relationships: How do you interact with the customer?
- Customer Segments: Who are the customers? What do they think, see, feel, and do?
- Key Partners: What can the company not do itself?
- Key Activities: What strategy does the business do to deliver its proposition?
- Key Resources: What unique strategic assets must the business have to compete?
- Costs and Revenues: What are the business' major cost drivers? How are they linked to revenue?

The heart of the BMC is to link and to relate the elements with each other and with the business model environment. This can be done by prototyping, testing and trials to develop the “first ideas” to a running business model. After a testing phase, the BMC and its elements are supposed to be adjusted.

Figure 3 Business Model Canvas. <https://strategyzer.com>, CC-copyright

Hereinafter, we introduce the second theoretical analysis framework, the promoters of innovation, and we demonstrate the practical application and development of a BMC in Vocational Education and Training by drawing on one of the c)-projects in chapter 3.

2.2 Promoters of innovation

Results of our first online survey, conducted in fall 2018 and executed by our project partner IIT in Berlin, show that 69% of the projects⁴ actually work on a project in their respective target country for the first time and only 31% have been active in the country during the last

⁴ This includes a), b) and c) projects.

five years. This means a large share of the organizations face the challenges of expanding to a new context and of having to establish new cooperations and connections with potential business partners, clients and local decision-makers such as government representatives. Engeström and Sannino (2010) include this perspective in the theory of expansive learning: “In expansive learning, learners learn something that is not yet there. In other words, the learners construct a new object and concept for their collective activity, and implement this new object and concept in practice.” (ibid., p. 2). Therefore, the authors focus on a development process which is oriented to a given context. Gessler (2017) calls this a *process-oriented approach* (ibid., p. 77). Our thesis is that the types of cooperation – fulfilled through different roles, called promotor – influence the success of a project. There are four types of promotor (Gessler 2019; Gemünden et al. 2006):

- Power promotor contribute through hierarchical power;
- Expert promotor provide expert knowledge;
- Process promotor arbitrate between technical and economic worlds by means of organizational knowledge;
- Relation promotor use extensive network competences to realize innovation.

Figure 2 shows the relationships of two systems, the starting system and the target system which include the four promotor roles each (Gessler 2019, p. 270). The connection is linked by the relation promotor. Fronting the promotor, there are opponents which can be persons as well as artefacts (like rigid routines), alternative concepts and strategies, and destabilizing contexts (e.g., political setting). This illustration can be used as an analysis tool to examine the process of transfer (new concepts, strategies, programmes etc.) with regard to its connectivity to the socio-cultural and education-political environment.

During the next years, the projects will be consulted recurrently about their promotor equipment and development on order to trace the evolution of the promotor’s roles during project implementation as well as innovative elements and transformed contexts. Additionally, the business model is supposed to influence the prospects of success, therefore the development and analysis of the projects’ business models are focused on as well.

Figure 2 Promotor and opponents in education transfer. Gessler 2019, p. 270.

Currently, 14 c)-projects (which started between mid-2017 and end-2018 and run three years usually) work on the issue: How can a vocational education and training-related service be placed on the market – a foreign, in many cases even unfamiliar market? The countries of interest are Greece, Spain, Serbia, Tunisia, Iran, Kazakhstan, China, South Korea, Brazil, Mexico, and the Philippines. This paper presents the case of a project in Serbia.

3 Case: project NEMID

NEMID⁵, a project which strives for the demand-driven development and implementation of a private dual VET school in Serbia, uses the BMC for its strategic planning.

Serbia's youth faces several challenges on the labour market: the share of youths in the Serbian population decreases and youths are disproportionately affected by unemployment – in 2015, the youth unemployment rate was 43,3% (Kovačević 2016).

3.1 NEMID and BMC

NEMID, which was initiated by the German publishing house Klett Präsenzlernen GmbH, considered the following aspects for the first design of the BMC:

Value Proposition. The product is a postsecondary theoretical vocational training in combination with productive workplace learning in a company. The duration is 2 years (see table 1). An accepted certification and good job prospects in the training company (for the trainees) as well as specialized junior employees (for the employer) are part of the proposition.

- **Channels.** A B2B (business to business) approach via chambers (PKS Serbian chamber of commerce; AHK Serbia) and direct contact with companies is used to reach customers.
- **Customer relationships.** Two focus groups need to be addressed in particular: teachers (VET school) and trainers (in-company trainers).
- **Customer segments.** The students in school and the companies are the customers whose needs the product (service) must be fulfilled.
- **Key partners.** Chambers (PKS; AHK) and ministries (German BMBF; Serbian Ministry for Education).
- **Key activities.** Theoretical training in professional expertise, methodical expertise and social expertise (in VET school); specific in-company training (workplace).
- **Key resources.** Teachers, teaching material, organization (VET school); trainers and company (company).
- **Cost structure:** For Klett, costs of ca. 150€/month/student will arise at full capacity; companies are supposed to pay school fees.
- **Revenue streams:** school fees paid by companies; revenue for companies results from the value added for the trainees during and after the training time.

⁵ The acronym NEMID stands for "Nachfrageorientierte Entwicklung und modellhaften Implementierung einer dualen Berufsschule in Serbien", which can be translated with "demand-driven development and model-like implementation of a dual VET school in Serbia".

Table 3 NEMID first business idea. Based on Ayen (2018).

Increment 1: 2 years postsecondary dual VET course	
year 1	year 2

After some months of project activity, as well as different interviews and feasibility checks with the German Chamber of Commerce (AHK, Außenhandelskammer) in Serbia and PKS, NEMID decided to adjust the original plans due to two facts: Firstly, the responses made clear that the heterogenous educational level of students were not considered. Secondly, a two-year school fee is too high a risk (and cost) for companies.

Therefore, an iterative process of BMC development was initiated: The product was modified towards a postsecondary VET school which is modularized and which offers pre-courses (to make up for deficits accumulated during secondary schooling), see table 2.

Table 4 NEMID second increment. Based on Ayen. (2018).

Increment 2: postsecondary dual VET course, modularized with pre-course		
Pre-course 4 weeks	Module 1 6 months	Module 2 6 months
	Module 3 6 months	Module 4 6 months

After professional content-related feedbacks, NEMID realized that a modularized form might be risky, because for companies, each module is a decision to invest (or to not invest) for the company. Hence, companies and trainees could tend to buy the pre-course and one or two basic courses and leave the VET school afterwards.

A third iteration followed: The VET school offers a pre-course (duration: 4 weeks) and a two-year course (see table 3).

Table 5 NEMID third increment. Based on Ayen (2018).

Increment 3: postsecondary dual VET course with pre-course and mid-term exam			
Pre-course 4 weeks	Year 1	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"> <tr> <td>Mid-term exam</td> </tr> </table> Year 2	Mid-term exam
Mid-term exam			

Considerations and responses of companies – which are supposed to eventually use the service finally – were positive, but they first wanted to ‘dip only a toe in the water’. Furthermore, companies do not want to pay for the entire amount of school fees. Therefore, a further adaptation of the service offer has been made (table 4):

Table 6 NEMID fourth increment. Based on Ayen (2018).

Here, students pay the pre-course themselves and companies pay for both years of training, additionally to a training wage for the trainees in the second year.

NEMID plans to start implementation of this concept in 2019 and the project is prepared to undergo additional conceptual changes. This actually is part of the approach: The content and framing of the service is customized to the context of Serbia and the companies operating in the country which will draw benefits from the VET service.

3.2 NEMID and promoters of innovation

For an analysis of the promotor roles in NEMID, the project genesis and the interaction with political actors are regarded. Besides, the promoters' roles in the iteration and modification process are being analyzed.

In the very beginning, there was the idea to sell educational services in south east Europe due to a predilection to this geographic region of the Klett board spokesman. Serbia has been chosen after a feasibility study has been made and for the reason of already existing networks to rely on. A subsidiary of Klett Präsenzlernen is Klett Eastern Europe with an affiliate in Serbia which sells textbooks successfully already. Now the business segment of vocational education and training is supposed to be added. Thus, companies are addressed as these announced the need of well trained youth employees. It is a main barrier to find partner companies that are not only searching for qualified employees but are also willing to pay for this resource.

Which political actors are involved? PKS, Serbian chamber of commerce supports the search for companies and carried out a company survey (500 businesses, 80% of these are German owned). Furthermore, close contacts to the Ministry of Education via a former Klett Serbia employee ensure the political backup for the project. This is not a direct help for NEMID, but has a legitimizing function.

For the continuation of the project, the branch manager of Klett Serbia is relevant as she can be identified as a relation promotor. She is responsible for client acquisition and the contacts to the political level. Furthermore, she is the process promotor of the Serbian project part. For the iterative process, she is not relevant so far, still it can be assumed that due to her process promotor role, she took on responsibility to pass the business model developments on.

The PKS network is also assessed to be relevant. Since 2017, there is the compulsory membership for companies in PKS. PKS is going to start certification of trainer's licences and NEMID wants to tie up at this point by training the trainers in the companies themselves in order to have direct contacts into the firms. The head of PKS is an important contact for NEMID who can be seen as a relation promotor as well. In-depth discussions with the head of PKS led to the first adjustment of the original business plan, leading to the second increment.

In Germany, there is an expert promotor who is responsible for the development of curricula. Besides, also in Germany, there is the process promotor who is the consortium leader of NEMID, belonging to Klett Präsenzlernen.

Opponents in NEMID can be described in the following way: In Serbia, it is not common for companies to pay for the qualification of their employees. So decision-makers might stick to their habits and possibly the power of imagination – how actually a system of VET operated by a company – is not sufficient to finally venture the investment.

Our thesis claims that each promotor role should be filled in the country of origin as well as in the country of interest for a successful implementation of VET services. At the moment, there is no expert promotor in Serbia. It is possible that an active process promotor in the country of interest can compensate this lack. Relation promotors presumably constitute an exceptional role without influencing the iterative adjustments directly. This role is filled in Serbia but not in Germany so far. Figure 2 shows that the link between a starting system and a target system is a relation promotor in both systems – this is not given in NEMID. Besides, a power promotor seems to be missing in the whole project.

4 Conclusions

Whether NEMID's business model will be successful cannot be foreseen at this stage. Also, it remains to be seen which shifts or developments of promotors will make progress and also which iterations of the business model are coming up. Our assumptions regarding promotors, their roles in the process of adaptation (adaptation of the business model) and the success of a project can neither be confirmed nor rejected so far.

Analyses of projects and their service developments using the BMC tool is expedient in service science approaches. Our thesis is that success and failure options as well as critical junctures can be determined in this way. At the moment, there is no forecast possible to predict the success or failure of NEMID. As our concomitant research will be able to evaluate the project also after project completion and retrospective reviews will be conducted.

Nevertheless, we conclude that in the context of VET-related services, the NEMID business model with envisaged redesigns and iterations works. The provided service is not part of the standard offers of the company, meaning it is being adopted to the target market. Different stakeholders are involved in the process of development and promotors are able to engage in the procedure. If an identification with the product by the whole organization would be important for the success of a service remains to be seen. This is a second step of development within the organization and could be an indicator for a continued existence of the business model after the funding period, which would finally determine the success of the project.

Likewise, it is necessary to regard macro-economic and comprehensive context knowledge when assessing and evaluating the performance criteria of a single project. Therefore, we use the preparation of context analyses (via desk research). We assume that there is a need for all our cases to be analysed in this way. Conclusions regarding BMC and promotor roles model will be possible then. Besides, both approaches for analysis – BMC and promotor model – are being regarded during a process (several surveys) which is beneficial to really assess the developments and decisive factors. Therefore, our VET-theory related approach in Service Science can be considered appropriate so far. To validate the method as gainful in

general, a wider appraisal is necessary with other cases unbiased by the funding program. This point also affects the limitation of our research: we did not choose justified cases ourselves, but we chose the ones that are part of the BMBF program. Due to this reason, scope and validity are limited hitherto.

In general, our concomitant research intends to make statements and offers political counselling with regard to future funding guidelines. Hence, our future research focusses the Service Science level (e.g., what makes VET-related science providers successful?) as well as the mentioned macro-level with potential systemic effects on the countries' VET systems.

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